

Synthesis of a few novel bioactive 2-substituted amino-5-indol-3-oyl-4-phenylthiazoles

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Manuscript received 11 January 2007, revised 5 July 2007, accepted 20 July 2007

Abstract : The 2-amino-4-arylthiazole motif is an important structural element in a variety of bioactive molecules. The (4+1) thiazole construction strategy adopted involves the synthesis of the [C–N–C–S] precursors, namely 1-aryl-3-(*N*-phenylbenzimidoyl) thiourea or 1-alkyl-3-(*N*-phenylbenzimidoyl) thiourea and the preparation of the C5 synthone, the halo acetylhetaroyl derivative. The optimized reaction conditions developed have thus lead to the preparation of five 2-(*N*-arylamino)-5-(indol-3-oyl)-4-phenylthiazoles and three 2-(*N,N*-dialkylamino)-5-(indol-3-oyl)-4-phenylthiazoles. The structure of these new compounds were assigned on the basis of elemental analysis, FTIR, ¹H NMR and ¹³C NMR and screened for their antimicrobial activity.

Keywords : Heterocyclics, thiazole, bioactivity, cytotoxicity.

Thiazole, a five membered heteroaromatic ring with nitrogen and sulphur has been of much interest to chemist and pharmacologists for long¹⁻³. Theonezolid A is a macrolide isolated from the marine sponge theonella sp shows cytotoxic activity against murine lymphoma and humen epidermoid carcinoma⁴. For example, the DNA cleaving ability of bleomycin⁵ is well known and other thiazoles, both natural and synthetic, also exhibit marked anticancer activity. Thiazolyindolequinone isolated from culture broths by Japanese workers was reported to have anticancer properties⁶. Since indolythiazoles are known to show interesting cytotoxic activity⁷, hitherto not reported indolythiazoles merit synthesis. This observations coupled with the interest we have in the synthesis of aroylthiazoles, prompted us to explore the synthesis of a new set of 2-aryl/alkyl substituted amino-5-hetaroyl-4-phenylthiazoles with a view to study their biological activity. A large number of structural variations are possible on the thiazoles skeleton with a variety of substituents at the C2, C4 and C5 positions. Hence, we decided to explore the possibility of a new series of compounds with a substituted amino group at C2, phenyl at C4 and an indolyl group at C5 to see the biological activity offered by them. The antibacterial screening was carried out following standard protocols using three bacterial strains.

Results and discussion

Synthesis of 2-(N-aryl/alkylamino)-5-(indol-3-oyl)-4-phenylthiazoles :

In the present strategy, the reaction between indolyl halide, either 3-chloroacetylindole **1** or 3-bromoacetylindole with 1-aryl-3-(*N*-phenyl benzimidoyl)thiourea **2a-e** was chosen. Since the reported preparation of 3-bromoacetylindole was tedious and low yielding, we explored the use of 3-chloroacetylindole¹² which could be prepared by an existing method modified by us.

In this synthetic procedure, **1** was reacted with the **2a-e** in *N,N*-dimethylformamide in the presence of triethylamine. The workup afforded yellow crystals of a compounds that had the molecular composition anticipated for the expected products **3a-e**. The FTIR, ¹H and ¹³C NMR spectrum were taken and were in agreement with the anticipated structure of the product. The reaction is represented as given below (Scheme 1).

Ar = **3a** : phenyl, **3b** : *o*-tolyl, **3c** : *m*-tolyl, **3d** : *p*-tolyl, **3e** : *p*-chlorophenyl

Scheme 1

The synthesis of 2-(*N,N*-dialkylamino)-5-(indol-3-oyl)-4-phenylthiazoles requires the preparation of *N,N*-dialkyl-*N'*-benzoylthiourea **4a-c**. The required **4a-c** was prepared by the reaction of benzoylisothiocyanate with dialkylamine. The benzoylisothiocyanate was prepared by using phase transfer catalyst and reacted with dialkylamine *in situ*.

4a : R = R' = Me; 4b : R = R' = Et; 4c : R = Me, R' = Ph

Scheme 2

The reaction of *N*-benzoyl-*N,N'*-dialkylthiourea with 3-(2-chloroacetyl)indole was carried out in dry acetone under reflux. The workup and purification by crystallization afforded the compounds as crystals 5a-c.

ind = indolyl; 5a : R = R' = Me; 5b : R = R' = Et; 5c : R = Me, R' = Ph

Scheme 3

The molecular compositions of the compounds were found to be in agreement with the compositions of expected ones.

The FTIR, ^1H and ^{13}C NMR were taken and were acceptable to the structures assigned. The ^1H NMR assignments were based on the data collected from the existing literature on indole⁸, 3-acetylindole⁹ and dendrodoine¹⁰ in the case of the indolyl group and that of 5-ketothiazole¹¹ for the thiazole moiety. The elemental analysis data of the synthesized compounds are tabulated in Table 1.

Antibacterial activity :

Out of the eight thiazoles that have now been screened for antibacterial activity against two Gram-positive bacteria *Sa* and *Bs* and one Gram-negative bacteria *E. coli*, four compounds were found to be active against *Bs* but all were inactive against *Sa* and *E. coli*. The results are tabulated in Table 1. It also appears that an aliphatic group on the amine attached to a C2 is better than an aryl group in imparting antibacterial activity.

Experimental

All chemicals used were of commercial grade. Melting points were uncorrected and were determined by open capillary method using an immersion bath of silicon oil or sulphuric acid. Thin layer chromatography was performed using silica gel-G (E. Merck, India) coated on glass plates. The spots were visualised in iodine vapour or under UV-light. The spectra were recorded on Bruker spectrospro-100 (100

Table 1. Elemental analysis and antibacterial activity of indolylthiazoles

Compd.	Molecular formula	Analysis (%) : Found (Calcd.)			Mol. wt. (O = 16.000 scale)	Organism (Compound 0.1 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$)		
		C	H	N		<i>Sa</i>	<i>Bs</i>	<i>Ec</i>
3a	C ₂₄ H ₁₇ N ₃ OS	72.62	4.21	10.53	395.47	R	6 mm	R
		(72.89)	(4.33)	(10.63)				
3b	C ₂₅ H ₁₉ N ₃ OS	73.20	4.58	10.12	409.49	R	R	R
		(73.32)	(4.68)	(10.26)				
3c	C ₂₅ H ₁₉ N ₃ OS	73.42	4.71	10.11	409.49	R	R	R
		(73.32)	(4.68)	(10.26)				
3d	C ₂₅ H ₁₉ N ₃ OS	73.12	4.58	10.16	409.49	R	R	R
		(73.32)	(4.68)	(10.26)				
3e	C ₂₄ H ₁₆ ClN ₃ OS	67.15	3.81	9.88	429.92	R	R	R
		(67.12)	(3.75)	(9.79)				
5a	C ₂₀ H ₁₇ N ₃ OS	69.28	4.81	12.31	347.43	R	9 mm	R
		(69.14)	(4.93)	(12.10)				
5b	C ₂₂ H ₂₁ N ₃ OS	70.22	5.42	11.08	375.48	R	9 mm	R
		(70.37)	(5.64)	(11.19)				
5c	C ₂₅ H ₁₉ N ₃ OS	73.14	4.72	10.35	409.49	R	9 mm	R
		(73.32)	(4.68)	(10.26)				

MHz), Bruker WM-400 (400 MHz) for ^1H and 100 MHz for ^{13}C , JEOL GSX (400 MHz) or EM-390 NMR spectrometers and JEOL D-300, JEOL SX-102, Shimadzu QP-2000, VG Micro mass 30F or ZAN IF mass spectrometers. All new compounds gave satisfactory C, H and N analysis (IIT, Chennai or CDRI, Lucknow).

Synthesis of 2-(N-arylamino)-5-(indol-3-oyl)-4-phenylthiazoles :

Preparation of 3-chloroacetylindole¹² :

Indole (20 mmol, 2.34 g) was dissolved in toluene (50 mL) containing 1.62 mL of pyridine at 55 °C. Chloroacetyl chloride (20 mmol, 1.6 mL) in toluene (5 mL) was then added to it drop by drop over a period of 1 h at 55 °C under stirring, which was continued another 1 h. Then a mixture of methanol (10 mL) and water (60 mL) was added to the flask and the stirring was continued, while a brown solid started to precipitate. It was filtered, washed with water and dried to get the crude product **1**, yield 2.78 g (72%). Crystallisation from ethanol-water provided light brown crystals m.p. 232–233 °C [lit.¹² m.p. 230–232 °C].

Preparation of N-phenylbenzamidine :

Benzonitrile and aniline were treated in a 250 mL flask in presence of anhydrous aluminium chloride. The reaction mixture was then heated at 180–200 °C for 30 min. The hot reaction mixture was poured into water containing concentrated hydrochloric acid under thorough stirring. The solution was decolorized by activated charcoal and poured in slow stream to a stirred solution of water containing sodium hydroxide. The flocculent precipitate was worked out as a white powder, m.p. 105–110 °C, yield 7.07 g (55%). The crude sample was crystallized from ethanol-water mixture (1 : 1), m.p. 111–112 °C.

Preparation of 1-aryl-3-(N-phenylbenzimidoyl)thiourea :

1-Phenyl-3-(N-phenylbenzimidoyl)thiourea **2a** was prepared as follows. N-Phenylbenzamidine (5 mmol, 0.98 g) was dissolved in N,N-dimethylformamide and phenyl isothiocyanate (5 mmol, 0.675 g, 0.6 mL) was added and the workup gave 1-phenyl-3-(N-phenylbenzimidoyl)thiourea, crude yield, 1.58 g (95%), m.p. 132 °C. It was then crystallized from ethanol-water mixture (1 : 2), 80%, m.p. 140 °C. The following imidoylthioureas were prepared using the method : 1-(o-tolyl)-3-(N-phenylbenzimidoyl)thiourea **2b** : yield 56%, m.p. 125 °C; 1-(m-tolyl)-3-(N-phenylbenzimidoyl)thiourea **2c** : yield 81%, m.p. 124 °C; 1-(p-tolyl)-3-(N-phenylbenzimidoyl)thiourea **2d** : yield 85%, m.p. 117 °C and 1-(p-chlorophenyl)-3-(N-phenylbenzimidoyl)thiourea **2e** : yield 96%, m.p. 124 °C.

Synthesis of 2-arylamino-5-(indol-3-oyl)-4-phenylthiazoles :

5-(Indol-3-oyl)-2-phenylamino-4-phenylthiazole 3a :

To a solution of **2a** (1 mmol, 0.34 g) in 5 mL N,N-dimethylformamide, **1** (1 mmol, 0.194 g) was added. The mixture was stirred well and kept at room temperature for 5 h. Triethylamine (2 mmol, 0.28 mL) was then added and the mixture was heated carefully at 55 °C for 1 h with occasional stirring afforded yellow precipitate with molecular composition $\text{C}_{24}\text{H}_{17}\text{N}_3\text{OS}$ on adjusting the pH. It was subsequently purified by crystallization from ethanol-water. Physical and spectral data of **3a**, yield 94%, m.p. 262 °C, IR (KBr) cm^{-1} : 3252, 3056, 2928, 1600, 1566, 1519, 1485, 1451, 1378, 1330, 1200, 1135, 892, 838, 751, 703, 617, 582; ^1H NMR (300 MHz, DMSO- d_6) δ : 7.04 (1H, t, J 7 Hz), 7.14–7.34 (6H, m), 7.34–7.48 (3H, m), 7.53–7.67 (2H, m), 7.67–7.82 (2H, m), 8.11–8.21 (1H, m), 10.64 (1NH, s), 11.87 (1NH, s).

5-(Indol-3-oyl)-4-phenyl-2-(o-tolylamino)thiazole 3b :

This was prepared as described above. Physical and spectral data of **3b**, yield 90%, m.p. 282 °C, molecular composition : $\text{C}_{25}\text{H}_{19}\text{N}_3\text{OS}$; IR (KBr) cm^{-1} : 3252, 3191, 3049, 2935, 1593, 1573, 1533, 1492, 1445, 1378, 1324, 1209, 1142, 912, 852, 757, 710; ^1H NMR (300 MHz, DMSO- d_6) δ : 2.33 (3H, s, Me), 7.04 (1H, t, J 7 Hz), 7.14–7.33 (5H, m), 7.34–7.49 (3H, m), 7.51–7.66 (2H, m), 7.68–7.82 (2H, m), 8.09–8.21 (1H, m), 10.63 (1NH, s), 11.86 (1NH, s); ^{13}C NMR (125 MHz, DMSO- d_6) δ : 20.39, 112.21, 116.20, 117.59, 117.85, 121.32, 121.88, 123.07, 125.85, 128.00, 128.18, 129.08(2), 129.54, 131.20, 125.18, 135.75, 136.50, 138.20, 140.65, 151.70, 151.89, 162.93, 163.28, 181.54.

5-(Indol-3-oyl)-4-phenyl-2-(m-tolylamino)thiazole 3c :

Yield 93%, m.p. 251 °C, molecular composition : $\text{C}_{25}\text{H}_{19}\text{N}_3\text{OS}$; IR (KBr) cm^{-1} : 3258, 3198, 3056, 2935, 1600, 1573, 1526, 1356, 1324, 1256, 1216, 1135, 905, 858, 757, 703; ^1H NMR (400 MHz, DMSO- d_6), ^1H NMR (400 MHz, DMSO- d_6) δ : 2.28 (3H, s, Me), 7.04 (1H, t, J 7 Hz), 7.1–7.33 (5H, m), 7.35–7.46 (2H, m), 7.52–7.66 (3H, m), 7.68–7.82 (2H, m), 8.10–8.20 (1H, m), 10.40 (1NH, s), 11.80 (1NH, s); ^{13}C NMR (125 MHz, DMSO- d_6) δ : 20.35, 112.16, 116.16, 117.53, 117.79, 121.28, 121.84, 123.02, 125.80, 127.94, 128.13, 129.04, 129.49(2), 131.14, 135.13, 135.70, 136.44, 138.14, 140.60, 151.67, 151.87, 162.88, 163.23, 181.49.

5-(Indol-3-oyl)-4-phenyl-2-(p-tolylamino)thiazole 3d :

Yield 94%, m.p. 267 °C, molecular composition : $\text{C}_{25}\text{H}_{19}\text{N}_3\text{OS}$; IR (KBr) cm^{-1} : 3191, 2948, 1654, 1533, 1445, 1283, 1243, 1155, 966, 805, 764, 649; ^1H NMR (400 MHz, DMSO- d_6) δ : 2.33 (3H, s, Me), 7.04 (1H, t, J 7 Hz, Ar-H),

7.15–7.25 (2H, m), 7.26–7.32 (3H, m), 7.35–7.45 (2H, m), 7.58–7.62 (1H, m), 7.67–7.75 (2H, m), 7.76–7.78 (1H, d, *J* 3.4 Hz), 8.10–8.17 (2H, m), 10.62 (1NH, s), 11.80 (1NH, s).

2-(*p*-Chlorophenylamino)-5-(indol-3-oyl)-4-phenylthiazole **3e** : Yield 95%, m.p. 257 °C, molecular composition : C₂₄H₁₆ClN₃OS; IR (KBr) cm⁻¹ : 3272, 3164, 3056, 2935, 1573, 1519, 1483, 1452, 1434, 1256, 1202, 1142, 1105, 1027, 905, 825, 744, 710, 661; ¹H NMR (400 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) δ : 7.00–7.25 (2H, m), 7.26–7.35 (2H, m), 7.36–7.50 (3H, m), 7.55–7.65 (2H, m), 7.70–7.74 (1H, d, *J* 7.8 Hz), 7.75–7.82 (2H, m), 8.10–8.18 (2H, m), 10.76 (1NH, s), 11.87 (1NH, s).

Synthesis of 2-alkylamino-5-(indol-3-oyl)-4-phenylthiazoles :

Preparation of *N*-benzoyl-*N,N'*-dialkylthiourea **4a-c** :

Benzoyl chloride (7.5 mmol, 0.8 mL) in benzene was stirred well and tetrabutylammonium bromide (TBAB; 0.2 g) was added. To this stirred mixture, aqueous solution of potassium thiocyanate (33%, 5.5 mL) was added in drops during 15 min. Stirring was continued for another 30 min. The aqueous layer was then removed using a Pasteur pipette. This was extracted with benzene and the benzene extract was added back to the main bulk. Dimethylamine (7.5 mmol, 0.34 mL) in benzene was added to the benzene layer in the flask and the mixture was stirred at room temperature for 2 h. It was then diluted slowly with pet. ether under slow stirring until the precipitation of thiourea was complete. The precipitate of *N*-benzoyl-*N,N'*-dimethylthiourea **4a** formed was then filtered, washed with pet. ether, dried and crystallised from EtOH/H₂O (20.9 g), yield 75%, m.p. 138 °C; **4b** : *N*-benzoyl-*N,N'*-diethylthiourea, yield 71%, m.p. 98 °C; **4c** : *N*-benzoyl-*N,N'*-methylphenylthiourea, yield 85%, m.p. 134 °C.

Synthesis of 2-(*N,N*-dialkylamino)-5-(indol-3-oyl)-4-phenylthiazoles :

A solution of **1** (1 mmol, 0.184 g) in dry acetone was refluxed with **4a-c** (1 mmol, 0.248 g) for 1.5 h. The reaction mixture was then cooled and added to ice-cold water and the pH of the resulting solution was adjusted to approximately 6. The precipitate thus formed was filtered, washed with water dried and crystallized from ethanol-water to obtain 2-(*N,N*-dialkylamino)-5-(indol-3-oyl)-4-phenylthiazole **5a-c**.

2-(*N,N*-Dimethylamino)-5-(indol-3-oyl)-4-phenylthiazole **5a** : Yield 56%, m.p. 235 °C, molecular composition :

C₂₀H₁₇N₃OS; IR (KBr) cm⁻¹ : 3184, 2935, 1639, 1527, 1432, 1283, 1243, 1148, 1094, 953, 740, 643.

2-(*N,N*-Diethylamino)-5-(indol-3-oyl)-4-phenylthiazole **5b** : Yield 72%, m.p. 220 °C, molecular composition : C₂₂H₂₁N₃OS; IR (KBr) cm⁻¹ : 2982, 2935, 2861, 1647, 1560, 1528, 1438, 1330, 1317, 1196, 1148, 1020, 899, 825, 757, 693, 670, 596, 427; ¹H NMR (300 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) δ : 1.24 (6H, t, *J* 7 Hz), 3.55 (4H, q, *J* 7 Hz), 7.14–7.35 (4H, m), 7.36–7.44 (1H, m), 7.47–7.58 (2H, m), 7.51–7.63 (2H, m), 8.07–8.15 (1H, m, H-4), 11.47 (1H, s, N-H).

5-(Indol-3-oyl)-2-(*N,N'*-methylphenylamino)-4-phenylthiazole **5c** : Yield 89%, m.p. 133 °C, molecular composition : C₂₅H₁₉N₃OS; IR (KBr) cm⁻¹ : 3191, 2955, 1654, 1580, 1526, 1438, 1391, 1283, 1243, 1162, 960, 798, 764, 643.

Antibacterial activity :

The bacteria strains selected to screen the antibacterial activity of thiazoles were two Gram-positive bacteria, *Staphylococcus aureus* (*Sa*), *Bacillus subtilis* (*Bs*) and one Gram-negative bacteria, *Escherichia coli* (*E. coli*). Agar disc diffusion method was followed for antibacterial susceptibility test. The results of the different thiazole samples screened are given in Table I. The bioactivity study has been confined to antibacterial testing as the *in vitro* cytotoxicity analysis, with external collaboration, is getting underway.

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